

Causal Banzhaf Value for aggregate query explanations^{*}

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Abstract

Aggregate queries, particularly those using averages, are essential for summarizing data and obtaining condensed information. Explaining such queries - by identifying how specific tuples, predicates, or combinations of predicates influence the result - provides deeper insights into the factors shaping query outcomes. However, existing statistical, interventional, and game theoretic explanation methods lack causal grounding, while causal methods require complete causal graphs, which are rarely available in large databases. To address this, we propose Causal Banzhaf Value (CBV): introducing causal awareness into Banzhaf values, our CBV method delivers explanations even in the absence of full causal graphs. Experiments on real world data demonstrate that CBV is computationally efficient, aligns with human intuition, and is consistent with causal explanations.

Keywords

Explainability, Query Answering, Data Analytics, Explainable Data Management

1. Introduction

The increasing reliance on data-driven decision-making in fields such as business, healthcare, and scientific research has amplified the importance of query explanations in understanding patterns, trends, and anomalies [1, 2, 3]. Aggregate queries, such as averages, sums, or counts, play a pivotal role in summarizing high-dimensional data but pose unique challenges for understandability. Analysts often need explanations to understand query results, such as the contributions of individual data segments or predicates, especially in high-dimensional datasets where interactions and dependencies are complex [4, 5].

Example Consider the Stack Overflow Developer Survey [6], a dataset which includes features such as age, developer role, years of coding experience, education level, and salary. An analyst might pose the aggregate query

```
SELECT AVG(Salary) FROM StackOverflow;
```

to retrieve the average salary. However, understanding why the average takes its specific value requires additional explanation; e.g., the predicate `Role = C-level Executive` might increase the result, while `Age = 25` might decrease it:

Predicate	Contribution to Avg. Salary
Education = Bachelor's	-15,000
Education = Master's	+15,000
Education =
...	...
Role = C-level	+22,500
...	...
Age < 18	-8,000
...	...

This explanation breaks down query results into additive or subtractive contributions of individual predicates to salary, enabling analysts to identify key factors and make informed decisions or policy recommendations. However,

accurately attributing the importance of individual predicates is challenging due to feature interdependencies and causal relationships. Existing techniques, such as DIFF [2] or MacroBase [4], fail to capture these dependencies, while game-theoretic methods like Shapley [7] and Banzhaf values [8] lack causal awareness [9]. Causal approaches, including XInsight [1] and CauSumX [10], rely on fully specified causal models, which are often computationally expensive and impractical to construct [3].

To address these limitations, we introduce **Causal Banzhaf Values (CBV)**, a novel approach for causally informed query explanations. CBV integrates causal knowledge to respect feature dependencies and employs conditional sampling [11] to estimate contributions accurately. For instance, it accounts for interdependence between Age and Education, ensuring causal information is reflected in the explanation. Unlike methods focusing on entire features, CBV evaluates the importance of specific predicates, offering more granular insights. For example, identifying that `Role = C-level` drives salary outcomes is more informative than attributing importance to the general feature `Role`. Moreover, CBV does not require a fully specified causal graph, making it suitable for scenarios where defining complete causal models is infeasible. Finally, CBV achieves computational efficiency, balancing accuracy with practicality for real-world applications.

2. Related Work

Approaches to explaining query results span statistical, relational, intervention-based, game-theoretic, and causal methods. Statistical techniques, such as DIFF [2] and MacroBase [4], find associations without causal insights. Relational methods, such as [12], trace data transformations through relational operations like joins, but lack the ability to provide causal explanations. Intervention-based approaches, such as Scorpion [13], detect outliers in aggregate queries but also lack consideration of causal relationships. Game-theoretic methods like Shapley values [14] and Banzhaf values [15], fairly attribute feature contributions by averaging marginal effects across subsets. While these approaches effectively capture interactions between features, they assume feature independence and disregard causal relationships [9]. Causal approaches, such as XInsight [1] and CauSumX [10], assume full causal models between all features. However, constructing complete causal models is challenging and often infeasible in practice [3].

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Our proposed CBV approach addresses these limitations by integrating partial causal knowledge into a game-theoretic contribution model. While full causal models are often elusive, some knowledge about causal feature interactions is usually available and provides valuable information.

3. Feature attribution

In explaining query outcomes, it is essential to determine how individual features influence a given result. The **Banzhaf Value**, rooted in cooperative game theory, provides a systematic way to quantify the influence of each feature as its marginal contribution. The change in value function $v : 2^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ across feature subsets, when including a particular feature $i \in N$ from the set of features $N = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, yields its Banzhaf Value β_i :

$$\beta_i = \frac{1}{2^{n-1}} \sum_{S \subseteq N \setminus \{i\}} [v(S \cup \{i\}) - v(S)],$$

where $v(S \cup \{i\}) - v(S)$ represents the marginal contribution of feature i to the subset S , and the sum iterates over all subsets S of N excluding i .

Please note that the related Shapley Value [14] weighs contributions based on subset sizes, which may overshadow the raw impact of features. The Banzhaf Value offers a more direct measure of their impact, relevant in a variety of application domains (see e.g. discussion in [15]).

Banzhaf Value (BV) offers a systematic framework for attributing contributions by evaluating all possible subsets of predicates. However, its limitations become evident when applied to aggregate query explanations. BV assumes independence among predicates, overlooking real-world dependencies, such as the relationship between `Age = 10` and `Education Level = Doctoral Degree`. This lack of causal awareness leads to misrepresentation of contributions. Additionally, BV distributes contributions symmetrically, failing to account for the hierarchical and asymmetric nature of causal chains (e.g., `Education` affects `Role`, which influences `Salary`). As a result, foundational predicates are undervalued. BV also incurs high computational overhead by evaluating all subsets exhaustively, which becomes impractical for high-dimensional datasets. CBV addresses these issues by integrating causal knowledge via partial DAGs to respect predicate dependencies, enabling accurate attribution. Unlike BV, CBV attributes contributions to specific predicate-value pairs, capturing their individual impacts while reflecting causal asymmetry. By focusing on causally valid subsets and using sampling techniques, CBV achieves efficiency without sacrificing accuracy. For predicates without causal ancestors, CBV defaults to BV, ensuring consistency.

4. Causal Banzhaf Value

Traditional Banzhaf value fairly attributes contributions by averaging marginal effects but assumes feature independence. For instance, in a causal chain where `Education Level` influences `Job Role`, which then affects `Salary`, it treats `Education Level` and `Job Role` as independent contributors, potentially misestimating their true impact.

To address this, we propose the Causal Banzhaf Value (CBV), which incorporates causal knowledge into the attribution process. Existing causal methods, such as XInsight

[1] and CauSumX [10], account for dependencies among features but face challenges in practice because they inherently rely on fully specified causal DAGs, which are often difficult or infeasible to construct, especially for complex datasets, or even completely unavailable, depending on the domain. Errors or omissions in the DAG structure can lead to incorrect attributions, reducing their reliability. Additionally, the computational demands of simulating interventional scenarios grow exponentially with data dimensionality, limiting scalability. CBV addresses these challenges by working with partial causal graphs, leveraging available knowledge without requiring complete DAGs. CBV focuses on causally valid subsets to maintain consistency and employs conditional sampling to estimate contributions efficiently. This combination of partial causal integration, flexibility, and computational efficiency makes CBV a robust and practical alternative to causal methods.

Unlike the application of Banzhaf value in Explainable AI [16], which focus on features, CBV evaluates the contributions of feature values (*predicates*). This aligns with query explanation needs, where specific feature values, such as `Role = C-level`, drive outcomes. CBV incorporates causal dependencies by considering causally valid coalitions (subsets) of features, defined based on a partial directed acyclic graph (DAG) G : for each feature i , we identify its ancestors $A_i = \{j \in N \mid j \prec_G i\}$, where \prec_G represents the causal ordering in G (see Figure 1 for an example). Then, we identify the set of all causally valid subsets for feature i , denoted as \mathcal{S}_i :

$$\mathcal{S}_i \leftarrow \{S \mid A_i \subseteq S, S \subseteq N \setminus \{i, Y\}\},$$

Thus, a subset S is valid if it contains all causal ancestors of i , A_i , and contains neither feature i itself nor the target variable Y . This ensures that attributions respect the known causal structure, while otherwise adopting the assumption of order independence as in the Banzhaf value for feature combinations where order is not known to impact outcomes. For example, $v(\text{Gender} = \text{Male} \mid \text{Education} = \text{Bachelor's}, \text{Age} = 25)$ is identical to $v(\text{Gender} = \text{Male} \mid \text{Age} = 25, \text{Education} = \text{Bachelor's})$.

The Causal Banzhaf Value (CBV) β_i^C for a predicate $p(i \text{ op } u)$ of feature i , a comparison operator op such as equality $=$, and value u is defined as:

$$\beta_{p(i \text{ op } u)}^C = \frac{1}{2^{n-1}} \sum_{S \in \mathcal{S}_i} \sum_{\mathbf{r} \in \mathcal{R}(S)} [v(S_{\mathbf{r}} \cup \{p(i \text{ op } u)\}) - v(S_{\mathbf{r}})],$$

where $\mathcal{R}(S)$ is the set of all possible realizations (value assignments) of features in subset S , and $v(S_{\mathbf{r}})$ is the expected value of the target variable Y conditioned on subset S with realization \mathbf{r} . For simplicity, we adopt the equality operator, i.e. predicate $p(i = u)$, in the following presentation.

To estimate $v(S_{\mathbf{r}})$ and $v(S_{\mathbf{r}} \cup \{p(i = u)\})$, we employ *conditional sampling* [11], which maintains feature dependencies and provides high estimation accuracy. For each subset S , realizations $\mathbf{r}^{(n)}$ are sampled from the empirical distribution $\hat{P}(S)$, while features not in $S \cup \{i\}$ are sampled conditionally as $\mathbf{x}^{(n)} \sim \hat{P}(X \setminus (S \cup \{i\}) \mid S = \mathbf{r}^{(n)})$. These samples allow the estimation of the expected value $v(S_{\mathbf{r}})$:

$$v(S_{\mathbf{r}}) \leftarrow \frac{1}{M} \sum_{n=1}^M Y(\mathbf{r}^{(n)}, \mathbf{x}^{(n)}),$$

and similarly for $v(S_{\mathbf{r}} \cup \{p(i = u)\})$, where $p(i = u)$ is fixed during sampling:

$$v(S_{\mathbf{r}} \cup \{p(i = u)\}) \leftarrow \frac{1}{M} \sum_{n=1}^M Y(\mathbf{r}^{(n)}, i = u, \mathbf{x}_{i=u}^{(n)}).$$

Figure 1: Partial causal DAG, adapted from the full causal model in [10] by removing one feature and several edges.

Here, $Y(\mathbf{r}^{(n)}, \mathbf{x}^{(n)})$ is the estimated value of target variable Y given a sampled realization $\mathbf{r}^{(n)}$ of the subset S , and $\mathbf{x}^{(n)}$, which includes the sampled values for all features not in $S \cup \{i\}$. This term reflects the target outcome based on the sampled configuration of the subset S and the conditionally sampled remaining features. Similarly, $Y(\mathbf{r}^{(n)}, i = u, \mathbf{x}_{i=u}^{(n)})$ captures target variable Y under the same realization of S , but with feature i explicitly set to value u . The term $\mathbf{x}_{i=u}^{(n)}$ corresponds to the sampled values of the remaining features conditioned on $S = \mathbf{r}^{(n)}$ and $i = u$. By setting $i = u$, this estimate reflects the impact of the specific value u for feature i on the target variable Y , considering the dependencies defined in the data distribution.

Example Reconsider our average salary query. CBV attributes contributions to predicates while respecting causal dependencies (Fig. 1). For $\text{Education} = \text{Master's}$, we find causally valid subsets $\mathcal{S}_{\text{Education}}$, and for each $S \in \mathcal{S}_{\text{Education}}$, the marginal contribution is computed as $v(S_{\mathbf{r}} \cup \{p(\text{Education} = \text{Master's})\}) - v(S_{\mathbf{r}})$, where $v(S_{\mathbf{r}})$ is the average salary conditioned on \mathbf{r} , the realization of predicates in S . CBV aggregates these contributions across all subsets and realizations to quantify the importance of $p(\text{Education} = \text{Master's})$, providing a causally consistent breakdown of how individual predicates contribute to the average salary.

Enumerating all subsets and performing conditional sampling can be computationally intensive, especially for high-dimensional datasets. To address this, We propose to approximate CBV by employing Monte Carlo sampling [17], which involves randomly selecting a suitable number of subsets M from \mathcal{S}_i and estimating the corresponding expected values. This approach balances efficiency and accuracy (Alg. 1).

5. Experimental evaluation

We implement Banzhaf Value (BV) [14] and Causal Banzhaf Value (CBV) using PyTorch with GPU acceleration on an NVIDIA T4 GPU, with 500 Monte Carlo samples for marginal contribution estimates via conditional sampling. Experiments are conducted on the Stack Overflow Developer Survey [6], a dataset offering insights into developer demographics, education, roles, and salaries, making it ideal for income analysis. Feature subsets were derived from a partial causal DAG, adapted from the complete version in [10], by excluding one feature and several edges to construct a partial causal model, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2 illustrates the BV and CBV contributions for the different features (plots (a)-(g)), detailed for different equality and range predicates. For features without ancestors in

Algorithm 1 CBV

Require: Dataset D , features $N = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, target variable Y ; partial causal DAG G ; number of samples M

Ensure: Contributions $\beta_{p(i=u)}^{\text{CBV}}$ for all features $i \in N$ and unique values for that feature $u \in U_i$

```

1: for  $i \in N$  do
2:    $A_i \leftarrow \{j \in N \mid j \prec_G i\}$ 
3:    $\mathcal{S}_i \leftarrow \{S \mid A_i \subseteq S, S \subseteq N \setminus \{i, Y\}\}$ 
4:   for  $u \in U_i$  do
5:     for  $S \in \mathcal{S}_i$  do
6:       for  $m = 1$  to  $M$  do
7:          $\mathbf{r}^{(n)} \sim \hat{P}(S)$ 
8:          $\mathbf{x}^{(n)} \sim \hat{P}(X_{\setminus(S \cup \{i\})} \mid S = \mathbf{r}^{(n)})$ 
9:          $Y^{(n)} = Y(\mathbf{r}^{(n)}, \mathbf{x}^{(n)})$ 
10:         $\mathbf{x}_{i=u}^{(n)} \sim \hat{P}(X_{\setminus(S \cup \{i\})} \mid S = \mathbf{r}^{(n)}, p(i = u))$ 
11:         $Y_{p(i=u)}^{(n)} = Y(\mathbf{r}^{(n)}, p(i = u), \mathbf{x}_{i=u}^{(n)})$ 
12:      end for
13:       $v(S_{\mathbf{r}}) \leftarrow \frac{1}{M} \sum_{n=1}^M Y^{(n)}$ 
14:       $v(S_{\mathbf{r}} \cup \{p(i = u)\}) \leftarrow \frac{1}{M} \sum_{n=1}^M Y_{p(i=u)}^{(n)}$ 
15:       $\beta_{p(i=u)}^{\text{CBV}} \leftarrow \frac{1}{2^{n-1}} [v(S_{\mathbf{r}} \cup \{p(i = u)\}) - v(S_{\mathbf{r}})]$ 
16:    end for
17:  end for
18: end for

```

the DAG (*race/ethnicity* and *age* in Fig. 2g and Fig. 2f), BV and CBV produce identical results, as causal dependencies are absent. Using feature contributions, we analyze cases where CBV and BV differ.

For *FormalEducation* (Fig. 2a), BV underestimates contributions of advanced degrees (*Doctoral*, *Master's*, *Professional*), and overestimates those of elementary and secondary school, by treating all effects as direct, ignoring downstream roles like *developer role*, and upstream roles like *Age*, which significantly drive salaries. CBV accounts for these causal links, producing causally consistent explanations. For *UndergradMajor* (Fig. 2b), BV overestimates contributions for fields like *Mathematics* and *Social Science*, which often affect salaries indirectly through roles or skills. CBV reduces these contributions while increasing contributions for fields like *Computer Science*, which have direct links to high-paying roles, aligning better with domain knowledge in the causal model. For *DevType* (Fig. 2c), BV misses the importance of roles like *Marketing* and *C-level*. CBV redistributes contributions, assigning higher values to roles like *C-level*, influenced by education and age (experience), and lower values to roles like *Marketing*. For *YearsCoding* (Fig. 2d), BV attributes all contributions directly to coding experience, inflating the importance of mid-level ranges (*12–14 years*, *15–17 years*). CBV incorporates the causal dependency of *YearsCoding* on *Age*, recognizing that older individuals naturally accumulate more experience, which indirectly influences salary. This adjustment results in more accurate contributions, reducing the inflation seen in BV. For *Student* status (Fig. 2e), BV suggests similar contributions for *full-time* and *part-time students*, which contradicts domain knowledge, as full-time students typically have less time for work and lower salaries. This issue arises because BV ignores *Age* as an ancestor of *student status* in the DAG, which appears to be the main cause for salary levels, whereas CBV contributions are in line with domain knowledge. For

(a) Predicates in Formal Education

(c) Predicates in Developer Type

(e) Predicates in Student

(f) Predicates in Race / Ethnicity

(g) Predicates in Age

(b) Predicates in Undergraduate Major

(d) Predicates in Years Coding

Figure 2: CBV and BV Stack Overflow predicate importance for salary. CBV obtains predicate importance in line with the partial causal model in Figure 1. Plots (a)-(e) show CBV finds notably different importance attributions where BV may result in misleading conclusions. For features in plots (f) and (g) without any ancestors in the causal model, BV and CBV results are identical (thus single bar only).

Figure 3: Runtime of predicate explanations aggregated per feature. CBV consistently outperforms BV.

race/ethnicity (*RaceEthnicity*, Fig. 2f) and Age (*Age*, Fig. 2g), BV and CBV results coincide exactly, as the DAG has no causal incoming edges for these features. Both methods highlight disparities in salary outcomes for e.g. *Native Americans* and higher age.

CBV offers significant computational efficiency over BV, as shown in Figure 3. By focusing only on causally valid subsets, CBV avoids unnecessary computations on infeasible configurations, resulting in a substantially reduced runtime. This improvement is especially notable for features with many causal dependencies, such as *developer role*. Even with Monte Carlo sampling applied to both methods, CBV

is faster as it limits sampling and evaluation to valid combinations, reducing overhead and effort. For features like *age* and *race/ethnicity*, which lack causal parents, BV and CBV produce identical results and a single bar represents the values for both in these two plots.

6. Conclusion and Future Work

CBV presents a novel efficient causally consistent method for predicate attribution for aggregate query explanations, addressing the limitations of traditional game-theoretic or causal methods. CBV integrates partial causal knowledge without requiring complete causal graphs, making it a valuable contribution in practice. In the following, we outline some limitations of interest for future work. While conditional sampling preserves feature dependencies and enhances accuracy, it introduces computational overhead, particularly in high-dimensional settings. CBV could also be extended to handle continuous domains directly, without the need to define predicate ranges (as e.g. for age). Another direction is enhancing CBV to provide explanations based on combinations of predicates to uncover feature interactions with high joint influence, offering richer insights into how multiple factors work together.

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